

UNIVERSITETLARDA TURIZM SOHASIDA INGLIZ TILINING ROLI

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Annotatsiya: *Ingliz tili yigirma birinchi asrning lingua francasi hisoblanar ekan, bugungi kunda hamma ingliz tilini mukammal bilishi kerak va professional ishga joylashish uchun, ayniqsa turizm sohasida ingliz tilini o'rgatishning ahamiyati yaqqol ko'rinib turibdi. Ingliz tili barcha malakali diapazonlarda talab qilinadi, lekin u o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tufayli tashrif buyuruvchilar sanoatida asosiy bo'lib qoladi.. Ingliz dialekti turizmni rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynadi va bu sohada ingliz tili sayohat uchun ham keng qo'llaniladi. mijoz bilan aloqada bo'lgani kabi va uchinchi darajali darajada qiziqish uyg'otadi. Ammo uning qiziqishi faqat turizm bo'yicha o'quvchilar bilan cheklanib qolmasligi kerak: turizm uchun ingliz tili - bu maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tilining (ESP) eng jozibali diapazonlaridan biri, chunki har birimiz bugungi kunda turli xil tadbirlarni tomosha qilamiz..*

Kalit so'zlar: *professional, turizm, ingliz tili, hudud, maqsad*

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: *As English is considered the lingua franca of the twenty-first century, everybody has to have a great command of English nowadays and the significance of instructing English for professional employments and especially within the field of tourism is evident. English capability is required in all proficient ranges but it gets to be fundamental within the visitor industry because of its particular characteristics.. English Dialect has played an critical part within the advancement of tourism and in this field, English is utilized broadly for travel as well as in client contact and is of outmost intrigued at the tertiary level. But its intrigued ought to not be limited to tourism understudies: English for tourism is one of the foremost alluring ranges of English for Particular Purposes(ESP) since, after all, all of us are sightseers on different events nowadays.*

Key words: *professional, tourism, English, area, purpose*

РОЛЬ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СФЕРЕ ТУРИЗМА В ВУЗАХ

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Аннотация: *Поскольку английский язык считается лингва-франка двадцать первого века, в настоящее время каждый должен хорошо владеть английским языком, и важность обучения английскому языку для профессиональной деятельности, особенно в сфере туризма, очевидна. Владение английским языком требуется во всех областях владения языком, но оно становится основополагающим в индустрии посетителей из-за его особых характеристик. Английский диалект сыграл решающую роль в развитии туризма, и в этой области английский также широко используется для путешествий. как в контакте с клиентом и чрезвычайно заинтригован на третичном уровне. Но его интрига не должна ограничиваться изучением туризма: английский язык для туризма является одним из самых привлекательных направлений английского языка для особых целей (ESP), поскольку, в конце концов, все мы сегодня являемся экскурсантами на различных мероприятиях.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональный, туризм, английский язык, область, цель*

English is the fourth most broadly talked local dialect within the world, and in terms of sheer number of speakers, it is the foremost talked official dialect. It is the essential dialect utilized in worldwide undertakings having official status indeed in countries where it isn't the essential talked dialect. English is undeniably the essential dialect of worldwide exchange and commerce and tourism since in

numerous nations, most tourism specialists and other authorities in contact with the open talk English to associated and lock in with visitors and foreigners. The progression of commerce and communication innovation within the course of past twenty a long time has revolutionized the field of English dialect educating and has drastically swerved the consideration of course creators from educating English for Scholarly purposes to educating for more specialized purposes, English for Particular Purposes(ESP). The educating of English for Scholastic Purposes (EAP) falls inside the system of what is by and large called English for Particular Purposes (ESP), taking put in substance, and as its title proposes, in an instructive environment. The reasons for its expanding pertinence is due to the reality that English has changed from essentially being another outside dialect into having gotten to be a all inclusive shape of communication in all strolls of life. Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998:95) state that the instructing handle of any kind of dialect for word related purposes ought to take as a beginning half quart the investigation of the four conventional abilities inside an suitable setting, that being, as distant as conceivable, the conditions given within the work environment. English for Word related Purposes (EOP) is more common compared to ESP since it does not center on the particular work disciplines but it is more based on common fundamental abilities required by understudies in arrange to be arranged for the workforce. Illustrations of fundamental abilities in EOP are the same as in ESP: perusing, composing, tuning in and talking. “ English for particular purposes may be a term that alludes to educating or considering English for a specific career(like law, medication) or for commerce in general”(International Instructor Preparing Organization, 2005). Pauline C.Robinson(1989) portrays ESP as a sort of ELT(English Dialect Educating) and defines it as “goal-oriented

language learning” which suggests that understudies have to be attain a particular objective within the prepare of learning. Concurring to the same creator, “Students ponder ESP not since they are curious about the English dialect as such but since they ought to perform a assignment in English. Their command of the English dialect must be such that they can reach a palatable level in their pro subject thinks about. The term "particular" in ESP alludes to the particular reason for learning English. Understudies approach the consider of English through a field that's as of now known and pertinent to them. This implies that they are able to utilize what they learn within the ESP classroom right absent in their work and thinks about. The ESP approach improves the pertinence of what the understudies are learning and empowers them to utilize the English they know to memorize indeed more English, since their intrigued in their field will propel them to associated with speakers and writings. ESP surveys needs and coordinating inspiration, subject matter and substance for the educating of important abilities. As a matter of truth, ESP combines subject matter and English dialect instructing. Such a combination is profoundly propelling since understudies are able to apply what they learn in their English classes to their fundamental field of ponder, whether it be bookkeeping, trade administration, financial matters, computer science or tourism. Being able to utilize the lexicon and structures that they learn in a significant setting strengthens what is instructed and increments their inspiration. Hutchinson and Waters as well draw the consideration to a “learning –centered approach” “in which all choices as to substance and strategy are based on the learner’s reason for learnig.An ESP program is subsequently built on an appraisal of purposes and needs and the capacities for which English is required . The point of ESP courses is to prepare the learners with a certain English

capability level for a circumstance where the dialect is reaching to be utilized, i.e., target needs (Sujana, 2005) . A number of ESP analysts have contended that as dialect completely different setting changes, strategies and substance of moment dialect instructing ought to change to meet the requirements of learners in particular situations(Hutchinson &Waters, 1987).According to the same creators, three terms can be utilized to clarify “needs”: “necessities”, “wants” and “lacks”. They characterize “necessities” as the sort of require decided by the demands of the target circumstance, that's , what the learner ought to know in arrange to work viably and effectively within the target circumstance. ESP concentrates more on dialect in setting than on instructing linguistic use and dialect structures. It covers subjects shifting from bookkeeping or computer science to tourism and commerce administration. Among the numerous professional zones that make the world of English for particular purposes, that of English for tourism is one of the foremost alluring since all of us are visitors on incalculable events, bringing our claim genuine encounters to the classrooms. Such a program, might, for case, emphasize the improvement of perusing aptitudes in understudies who are planning for graduate work in trade organization; or it might advance the advancement of talked aptitudes in understudies who are considering English in arrange to gotten to be visitor guides. The central point of instructing English for tourism is that English isn't instructed as a subject isolated from the students' genuine world ; instep, it is coordinates into a subject matter area imperative to the learners. Within the field of English for tourism students most of the ponders have centered on the examination of the specified abilities and needs in work put, ampleness and fittingness of directions materials and procedures. Al-Khatib (2007) inspected the communicative needs of tourism and managing an account faculty

by shedding lights on their recognitions of needs, needs, needs, and states of mind toward English in arrange to incorporate what is required and avoid what considered less vital to them. It has been watched that the sort of work plays a noteworthy part in assessing and utilizing of English. The foremost common reasons for communicating as a travel office laborer were found to be advertising goal guides, composing and sending e-mail and faxes, making on-line ticketing, browsing the web, making online inn booking, etc. Travel office clients were found to be heavier clients of English than their managing an account partners. The comes about of the study indicated that the foremost critical expertise for tourism faculty is composing. When guideline an EOP course an issue to require into thought is that utilizing satisfactory language learning and proficient strategies are required in tourism field). In planning a course for understudies of culture and tourism, Barancic utilized an coordinates approach to induce the understudies included within the syllabus he needed to instruct. The approach he concocted comprised of 8components: knowing the course and their information, deciding the objectives to accomplish, the way we degree the victory, making choices with understudies included, making syllabus, choosing on the genuine educating procedures and strategy and getting criticism amid the course. The application of the approach shown that the instructors are confronted with needs which are of a less scholarly and more reasonable nature. Understudies of tourism ought to be mindful of the colossal significance of English in their instruction since it is an basic instrument in any field of their future movement: administration, visitor data, advancement of traveler goals, middle person companies, neighborliness and transportation, etc .Subsequently, understudies of tourism ought to be exceedingly propelled to memorize English and in spite of the fact that more regularly they will

probably focus on verbal instead of composed abilities, in their career they must be able to expand composed records such as letters or budgets, they ought to keep phone discussions, make introductions to groups of onlookers, go to fairs and conferences and get it all sorts of composed data on visitor goals. For case, understudies of tourism can be instructed commonsense English discussion utilized in lodging and catering industry, different issues concerning tourism industry , recommendations on work interviews and writing resumes, perusing and understanding articles concerning such issues of tourism. Usually due to the students' desire to improve talking English and their ought to learn English for future employments instead of utilizing it in way of life. Great fabric ought to be based on different curiously writings and exercises giving a run of aptitudes, one piece of fabric serving for creating more than one expertise, e.g. perusing, tuning in, talking, composing. Writings as learning materials can be utilized for learning and practicing a wide run of abilities. In ESP course, they can be sources for unused lexicon, communicative or perusing aptitudes. They can trigger different exercises: warming –up activities(pre-teaching and enactment of unused lexicon or linguistic use structures, examining questions concerning the topic);receptive activities-work with the content itself, perusing, listening(various perusing methodologies e.g. out loud, calm, skimming, checking, with or without interpretation, instructive; profitable activities-practising of procured information, follow-up activities-next moving forward, creating, utilizing of procured information. In conclusion, carefully recognized needs and fitting educating materials for tourism understudies will create not as it were fulfilled clients but moreover bounty of proficient fulfillment in their future career.

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